

Research Plan

Title: Former unaccompanied minors and the transition to adulthood: Perspectives and insights from the lived experience in Finland

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Introduction

There are two research objectives linked to the action of this research. Research Objective 1 (RO1) is to better understand the transition to adulthood of former unaccompanied minor youth in Finland. The participants of this study sought asylum as unaccompanied minors but are now young adults – as such, are now technically former unaccompanied minors. Using a qualitative voice-centred relational methodology (VCRM), RO1 will address the following research questions: *‘How do former unaccompanied minor youth in Finland conceptualise the transition to adulthood?’*; *‘What do former unaccompanied minor youth in Finland identify as barriers and supports to the transition to adulthood?’* Research Objective 2 (RO2) is to innovate new ways of co-constructing knowledge and art with participants, addressing the following research question: *‘How does the collaborative creation of knowledge through a*

participatory arts-based method amplify the voices of former unaccompanied minor youth in Finland? Better understanding the transition to adulthood of these youth is important, as a smooth transition to adulthood has been linked to social and economic success as well as wellbeing in the adult years (UNESCO, 2015).

Unaccompanied minors are youth under the age of eighteen who have sought asylum without a parent or guardian. These youth transition into adulthood in their new home countries without the support of their biological families. In my previous research, I have explored how Sudanese and South Sudanese refugee youth, who have migrated with their families, experience becoming adults in Australia (Macaulay, 2020). For these youth, the purpose of being an adult meant being able to contribute within their communities. These collective conceptualisations of the purpose of being an adult focused on the importance of relationships, especially with immediate family. Given these findings, to progress the state-of-the-art of our knowledge it is crucial to better understand these experiences from the perspectives of unaccompanied minor youth. Given they lack parental relationships in their country of settlement, it is important to understand which sources of support they utilise. Furthermore, the methodology and participatory paradigm (see methods section below), have been carefully chosen to champion voices that are virtually silent in this research, that is, those of these youth – addressing this gap in the research.

Europe is currently receiving the highest numbers of refugees and asylum seekers since World War Two (Flåøyen, 2022). The year 2015, also known as the year of the ‘refugee crisis’ in Europe, increased the number of unaccompanied minors coming to Finland tenfold. More recently, Russia’s 2022 invasion of Ukraine intensified this situation and brought different groups of humanitarian migrants to Finland, with many children and youth arriving unaccompanied (Finnish Immigration Service, 2023). While previous research has demonstrated that refugee youth may settle fast (Deng, 2016), the absence of family can influence how these young people build their overall identity and their wellbeing as young adults. Calls have been made to better address the wellbeing of unaccompanied refugees at Finnish (de Arruda Camara et al., 2018), Nordic (Rehn-Mendoza, 2020) and broader European (Vervliet et al., 2014) levels, all repeating similar concerns: The starting point of much youth policy is that young people can rely on their families far into adulthood (Malm, 2018). Moreover, many of the

receiving countries, including Finland, are traditionally rather homogenous (Korkiamäki & Kaukko, 2023). This homogeneity and family-centredness positions the experiences of unaccompanied refugee youth at the margins, making it difficult to capture these experiences with commonly used methods. Therefore, it becomes imperative to develop methods to understand the cultural and familial nuances that shape the transition to adulthood of unaccompanied asylum-seeking youth, and ensure these voices reach policy and practice.

This study is theoretically underpinned by Yuval-Davis's (2006) concepts of political belonging and Yuval-Davis et al.'s (2019) concept of bordering. For Yuval-Davis (2006) belonging is defined as "emotional attachments" and "feeling at home" (p. 197). Importantly, social locations and their intersections (e.g., race, gender, socio-economic status) are not inherently linked to belonging. Rather, it is when these social locations are contextually politicised that they influence belonging, giving rise to a politics of belonging. In Finland, people from asylum-seeking backgrounds can experience this form of identity politicisation (Petäjänieniemi et al., 2021). For unaccompanied asylum-seeking youth, this may result in discrimination undermining their overall sense of belonging and safety as well as subsequently impeding a positive construction of identity as they transition to adulthood. This study is novel in using Yuval-Davis et al.'s (2019) concept of bordering to understand how youth navigate the individual, collective, social, and political intersections of everyday lived experience as they become adults. Broadly speaking, bordering can be thought of as the concrete and abstract borders that are created and maintained within societies, which can curate – at times unevenly – the everyday lived experiences of belonging and a sense of safety. For participants in this study, these borders may be physical borders – such as those that demarcate their physicality relative to geography and concepts of home. Additionally, these borders may also be the abstract borders of everyday experience – such as the social conditions that generate marginalisation, or conversely, social conditions and agency that promote a sense of inclusion and community. Of interest is how young people experience these borders – including reinforcing and eradicating them to build communities that aid a smooth transition to adulthood.

Methods

This research utilises a qualitative single-site case design underpinned by a voice-centred relational methodology (VCRM) (Brown & Gilligan, 1991). In VCRM the voice is investigated in relation to itself, with others, and with broader social and cultural systems and structures. The rationale for using VCRM is that it amplifies voices that have previously been silent in this discussion – those of young refugees, and places them at the centre of research while also acknowledging the intersecting and multi-layered components of their voices. Additionally, previous research has demonstrated that VCRM approaches are both useful and ethical when working with populations whose voices may be marginalised within their societies (Gilligan et al., 2003). While the social and political histories of refugee youth may result in vulnerability, being a refugee is not an inherent quality of vulnerability. Participants' self-determination will be respected regarding their capacity to offer informed consent to participate, including their capacity to be involved in aspects of data analysis and the communication of findings.

Approximately 20 participants will be recruited into this study via a convenience sampling approach from multiple locations in Finland. While the target sample size of participants is 20, the planned study can be conducted with as few as 10-15 participants. This sample size has been determined by the depth required in VCRM approaches (Mauthner & Doucet, 2011). As detailed in the following paragraphs, a single interview transcript will be analysed four times from four different perspectives as well as being constructed into poems. Anything beyond the proposed sample size would not allow for this level of depth and could not be completed in the 24-month timeframe. The sample will include participants who sought asylum in Finland as unaccompanied minors, are over the age of eighteen, and are fluent in English at a minimum B1 level as per the Common European Framework of Reference for Language skills (European Union, 2024). Women are underrepresented in unaccompanied minor communities around the globe, which reflects gender imbalances in research. The voices of unaccompanied young women are scarce within the research literature. If possible, it will be ensured that approximately half of the participants in this study will

be women. I will also welcome individuals with diverse and ‘non- traditional’ gender identities to participate.

Aligning with the two objectives of this study, data will be collected and analysed in two phases. Phase one (RO1) consists of individual semi-structured interviews. Interviews will be transcribed and analysed using the VCRM perspectives proposed by Brown and Gilligan (1991), which are as follows: ‘*The story of who is speaking?*’ From this perspective, transcripts are read to identify any overarching themes or concepts within the participants’ narratives; ‘*In what body?*’ From this perspective, transcripts are analysed for specific instances of when and how individuals speak about themselves; ‘*Telling what story about relationships?*’ From this perspective, transcripts are analysed for specific instances of when and how individuals speak about others; and ‘*In which societal and cultural framework?*’ In consideration of the previous perspectives, transcripts are analysed to identify any overarching social/cultural frameworks in which participants contextualise their narratives.

The analysed transcripts will then be written as *pronoun poems*, a novel VCRM approach I developed in my PhD research, which is presented in several of my publications (see for example Macaulay, 2021, 2023; Macaulay & Deppeler, 2020, 2022). Given that a fundamental principle of VCRM approaches is that the voice is multi- layered, *pronoun poems* will be constructed to better understand these layers. The use of *I poems* is common in VCRM approaches; however, the focus is exclusively on the first-person *I* pronoun. I found these poems to be limiting when working with communities whose relational ontologies and epistemologies are underpinned by culturally collective worldviews (such as many of the potential participants in this study). Utilising *pronoun poems* will accommodate a variety of pronouns to acknowledge the range of important relationships, as well as giving me the capacity to continue my development of the VCRM method in a new context with different cultural cohorts.

When constructing *pronoun poems* three different uses of pronouns will be of interest. First, accounting for personal experiences using a first-person voice. Second, accounting for personal experiences using a second-person voice. Third, accounting for personal experiences using quotes/mimicry. *Pronoun poems* will be developed by underscoring pronouns and placing these on their own line with surrounding verbs

and/or other important words to create stanzas. Interested participants will be invited to take part in data analysis and poem construction and will be taught the method accordingly. It has been argued that participatory approaches – such as this – not only promote analytic/theoretical rigour and reduce the potential impact of biases, but also promote social justice via the inclusion of potentially marginalised individuals in processes of social research (Kaukko & Fertig, 2016).

In phase two, linked to RO2, the knowledge produced in phase one will be turned into artistic outputs. Participants will be invited to showcase their *pronoun poems* in a book including analytic commentaries written by me in consultation with participants. Participants will select a *pronoun poem* and justify their reasons for choosing their poem. These justifications will be included in the analytic commentaries. Next, visual artists will be invited to produce a visual interpretation of a *pronoun poem*, which will feature alongside the respective *pronoun poems* and analytic commentaries. Recruiting visual artists with similar lived experiences as participants of the study will be prioritised. Visual artists will present their artwork to the participants, while I interview both in an open-ended paired interview. All paired interview transcripts will be analysed using the four VCRM analysis steps detailed earlier. The purpose of this approach is to better understand the collective voices, processes, and interpretations of how the co-construction of knowledge through a participatory arts-based method amplifies the voices of former unaccompanied minor youth in Finland. The book will be launched at an event, open to the public, where participants can offer a reading of their poems as well as display the artwork linked to their poems. Respecting the self-determination and contributions of participants means that if participants wish to be named as co-authors of their poems, this request will be granted. While this compromises participants' anonymity, previous research has highlighted the ethical importance of giving participants the option to take credit for their work in participatory research (i.e., to anonymise voices against the participants' wishes, in some instances, is to silence them) (Kaukko, 2023; Korkiamäki & Kaukko, 2023). To ensure that participants can make an informed decision, I will carefully explain the risks and benefits of anonymised and non-anonymised involvement.

Sharing of Results

The findings of this research will be disseminated to the scientific community in a minimum of six open access journal articles throughout and beyond the action of the research. These articles will be submitted to journals in the fields of youth studies, intercultural studies, and forced migration studies. Additionally, papers will be presented at a minimum of three international academic conferences. Journals and conferences will be chosen based on their congruence with the proposed research, their scholarly reputations, and their capacity to communicate findings to international interdisciplinary audiences.

The findings of this study can be utilised by policy makers and practitioners who work with unaccompanied minors in Finland, Europe, and elsewhere. Towards the end of the action of the research an event will be planned where summary reports of findings will be launched in Finnish and English. This event will include a roundtable discussion with key stakeholders such as participants (and their communities), policy makers, educators, youth, and refugee community organisation representatives.

Central to participatory arts-based methods is to communicate research findings to broad audiences beyond academic dissemination. A project website, including a blog about the progress of the research, and research findings when available, will be launched at the start of the action. Further, the book of poems and visual art developed alongside participants will be a crucial component of communicating findings. Including participants in the communication of findings through this book is important to ensure that they are active non-objectified agents in communication strategies. Participants will be encouraged to share this book with their wider community networks. Participants, the supervisor, and I will share in the intellectual property of this book

Impact

The findings of this study will have scientific/theoretical impacts as they will incorporate previously unheard voices, those of unaccompanied minor youth to the growing body of literature on the transition to adulthood. This contribution can assist social scientists to better understand the cultural and family-related nuances of the transition to adulthood

and to be cautious of the lens(es) they adopt in their research, as well as assisting in how to use participatory research methods with refugee youth in an ethical manner across a variety of disciplines (e.g., education; youth studies; refugee studies). Therefore, this research will set a foundation that has the capacity to inform future research at a global magnitude beyond the immediate scope and duration of this project. Particularly, the chosen methodological design can inform future projects with participants whose voices may be silent/silenced in scholarly discourses.

Further, the findings of this research have the capacity to have social impacts beyond the scope of the action. Statistics indicate steady increases of forcibly displaced people around the globe, with this trend predicted to continue in the coming years with growing numbers of people seeking asylum in Europe (UNHCR, 2024). Given these trends, this research and its findings will contribute to the UN's Sustainable Development Goal of Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions, stating that people should be free of fear from all forms of violence and feel safe as they go about their lives. Culturally responsive knowledge about the transition to adulthood as experienced by unaccompanied youth can contribute to the design of socially and culturally responsive supports aimed to assist these youth to experience a safe and smooth transition, which in turn is linked with social prosperity, such as a sense of societal belonging, overall wellbeing, and social engagement within one's society. Better understanding the belonging and identity construction of refugee youth throughout this transition can aid in promoting authentic and just societal inclusion. This impact will be achieved by targeting social workers, educators, and other practitioners. Social impact will be strengthened as I unpack the participatory design, in order to enable practitioners and researchers to tune their ears to hear the nuances of the voices of unaccompanied youth. The small sample size and the participatory approach will enable these deep insights. Further, the importance of this research has potential magnitude beyond Finland and may influence an understanding of social inclusion in other European contexts, specifically in the Nordic region.

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